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ROLE OF VEGAN DIET IN HEALTH AND DISEASES- REVIEW PAPER

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Abstract

Vegan diet is one in which all or most of the meals are sourced from plants. This eating style may be good for one's health as well as the environment. It is beneficial to the immunological system. Plants provide essential components that cannot be obtained from any other source. Vitamins, minerals, phytochemicals, and antioxidants found in plant assist in keeping cells vigorous with the body balanced, helping his defense system can perform optimally. The term "vegan diet" refers to a number of dietary patterns that emphasise plant-based foods such as veggies, fruits, whole grains, legumes, nuts, and seeds in place of animal products. However, The term "plant-based diet" has developed eventually, with instances of the term being used to refer to vegan diets (which contain exclusively plant-based foods and no animal products), vegetarian diets (which may include dairy or eggs but no animal products), and diets that include limited amounts of animal-based foods, such as semi-vegetarian and authentic Mediterranean diets, can be found. Plant-based diets are being studied in the early stages to see if they may enhance metabolic parameters in health and illness, as well as if they have long-term impacts on diabetes. The cognitive and mental consequences vegan foods remain uncertain. When the emphasis was on whole meals, diabetes indicators improved, as did obesity. Plant-based diets have been related to enhance mental and physical well-being, depression treatment, improved quality of life, and overall health among diabetics.

Keywords: Vegan Diet, Types and Function, Health Benefits.

Introduction

Vegan diet, often known as a plant-rich diet, consists primarily of plant-based foods. Plant-based foods are those that are made entirely of plants (such as vegetables, grains, nuts, seeds, legumes, and fruits) and do not contain any animal products or artificial chemicals. While a vegan diet excludes or limits animal products, a plant-based diet is not always vegan. Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics reported that properly-planned plant-based diets are beneficial to health at all phases of life, including pregnancy, breastfeeding, youth, and adulthood, as well as for athletes. As of the early twenty-first century, it is believed that 4 billion people eat predominantly a plant-based diet, some by choice and others due to agricultural, fresh water, and energy resource constraints. Consumption of plant-based meat replacements in Europe accounted for 49% of the global market in 2020 and is expected to increase by 60% by 2025, owing to concerns about health, food security, and animal welfare. The retail market for plant-based foods is worth \$7.4 billion, up from \$6.9 billion in 2020. T. Colin Campbell claim to be the inventor of the phrase "plant-based diet" in 1980 to assist him convey his diet study at the National Institutes of Health. He described it as "a low-fat, high-fiber, vegetable-based diet that prioritised health over ethics." "I offered cooking workshops for the national non-profit The Physicians Committee for Responsible Medicine (PCRM) and at that time, the phrase 'plant-based diet' started to be used as aeuphemism for vegan eating, or "the 'v' word," said vegan author Ellen Jaffe Jones in a 2011 interview. It was created to de-emphasize the word "vegan" since some people connected it with having an extreme attitude focused solely on animal rights rather than health considerations.

Veganism: Diet that is free of all animal products, including meat, fish, poultry, eggs, and dairy products. Consumption of whole foods is not required, nor is there a restriction on fat or processed sugar.

Fresh foods, vegetarian: Exclusions are the same as for veganism, plus all items cooked at temperatures over 118°F.

Dairy: Includes milk products but excludes eggs, meat, shellfish, and poultry.

Ovo-vegetarian: Includes eggs and excludes meat, fish, poultry, and dairy items.

Lacto-ovo vegetarians eat eggs and dairy products instead of meat, fish, and fowl.

Mediterranean: A plant-based diet that permits limited amounts of poultry, dairy products, eggs, and red meat once or twice a month. Olive oil and fish are recommended. There are no restrictions on fat.

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Whole-foods, plant-based, low-fat diet: Encourages the consumption of plant foods in their whole, particularly vegetables, fruits, legumes, seeds, and nuts (in smaller amounts). This diet restricts animal products for maximum health advantages. The amount of total fat in the body is normally limited.

Advantages of Vegan diet

As a result of unhealthy lifestyles, obesity, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease are all on the increase. We define a vegan diet as a way of life that emphasises entire, plant-based meals while avoiding meat, dairy, and eggs, as well as any refined and processed foods, may be the greatest way to eat healthy. Vegan diets have been reported in studies to be cost-effective, low-risk therapies for lowering BMI, blood pressure, HbA, and cholesterol levels. They may reduce the amount of medicines needed to manage chronic diseases, which might help reduce ischemic heart disease death rates. Our diet should be tailored to improve our overall health. Our evaluation includes studies on vegan, vegetarian, and Mediterranean diets that have already been published.

Obesity

A plant-based diet was proven to be useful in treating obesity in a 2021 research. Only the vegan demonstrated a substantial weight decrease of 6.5 kg after 4 months (14.33 pounds). Those who ate a plant-based vegan diet lost more weight and improved their insulin sensitivity, but those who ate a meat-based diet did not. The Oxford component of the European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition looked at weight and BMI changes in men and women in the UK who ate meat, fish, vegetarians, and vegans during a five-year period. "Epidemiologic research reported that vegan diets are connected with a lower BMI and a decreased obesity incidence in adults and children," Sabaté and Wien write. A meta-analysis of adult vegetarian diets found, men lost 7.6 kg and women lost 3.3 kg, resulting in a 2-point reduction in BMI. Similarly, vegetarian children are slimmer than non-vegetarian children, and the BMI disparity grows during puberty. According to research analysing the risk of overweight and food categories and dietary patterns, a plant-based diet appears to be a practical technique for the prevention of childhood obesity.

Diabetes

vegan diets may help insulin sensitivity and reduce insulin resistance, which may help people avoid or manage diabetes. Diabetes can be managed with vegan diet. Vegetarian and vegan diets, according to the authors of a 2018 analysis, may assist persons with diabetes reduce their medication usage, lose weight, and improve other metabolic parameters. In terms of diabetes prevention and control, plant-based diets may have an advantage over non-plant-based diets. Adventist Health Studies reported that, vegetarians have about 50% chance of diabetes as non-vegetarians. Vang et al. observed in 2008 showed non-vegetarians were 74% more likely to eat meat than vegetarians to acquire diabetes during a 17-year period.

Heart Disease

In the Lifestyle Heart Trial, Ornish observed that 82% of those with documented heart disease who followed his regimen saw atherosclerosis regression. Comprehensive lifestyle modifications seems to be impetus for even in the case of significant coronary occlusion to retreat after just one year. In his plant-based diet, fat accounted for 10% of calories, protein for 15% to 20%, and carbohydrate for 70% to 75%, with cholesterol limited to 5 mg for each day. Surprisingly, atherosclerosis progressed in 53 percent of control group. The experimental group's stenosis dropped from 37.8% to 34.7 percent after 5 years (a 7.9 percent relative improvement). The stenosis in the control group increased from 46.1 percent to 57.9 percent (a 27.7 percent relative worsening). The intervention group's Mediterranean-style diet comprised of more plant foods, vegetables, fruits, and fish than meat. Canola oil margarine was used in place of butter and cream. Only canola and olive oils were suggested as fats. vegetarian diets are linked to a decreased risk of various chronic illnesses, diverse types of vegetarians may have diverse health outcomes. The most important thing is to concentrate on eating a balanced diet rather than a vegan or vegetarian one.

Mortality

Huang et al. conducted a meta-analysis in 2012 to compare the death rates of vegetarians and non-vegetarians due to cardiovascular disease. Only trials reporting relative risks and 95% confidence intervals will be included in the study. Vegetarians had a 29 percent lower death rate from ischemic heart disease than non-vegetarians. The Dietary Guidelines Advisory Committee looked studied the impact of plant-based diets on stroke, cardiovascular disease, and overall mortality in adults in a 2010 literature review. They observed that plant-based diets were connected to a decreased risk of cardiovascular disease and mortality when compared to non-plant-based diets.

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Vegan Diets and Health Concerns Protein

Protein deficit is rare in patients those who eat a plant-based diet. Amino acids are the building blocks of proteins, and certain of them, known as the body cannot synthesise necessary amino acids, hence they must be obtained through food. Essential amino acids are found in meat, dairy products, and eggs, as well as many plant-based meals like quinoa. Consuming particular plant-based dietary combinations can also provide essential amino acids. Two examples are brown rice with beans and hummus on whole wheat pita. As a consequence, a well-balanced plant-based diet will provide sufficient amounts of essential amino acids to avoid protein deficiency.

Iron

Plant-based diets include iron, although it is less bioavailable than iron contained in meat. Iron-rich plant-based meals include kidney beans, black beans, soybeans, spinach, raisins, cashews, oats, cabbage, and tomato juice. Iron stores may be depleted in those who follow a plant-based diet with little or no animal sources. According to the American Dietetic Association, iron deficiency anaemia is uncommon even among plant-based eaters.

Vitamin B 12

Vitamin B12 is needed for the formation of red blood cells as well as cell division. Vitamin B12 deficiency is a serious problem that can cause macrocytic anaemia and irreversible nerve damage. Vitamin B 12 is produced by bacteria rather than plants or animals. People who follow a plant-based, meat-free diet may be at risk for B12 deficiency and may need to supplement their diet with vitamin B or foods supplemented with vitamin B 12.

Ca and Vitamin D

In a well-balanced, well-planned plant-based diet, calcium consumption can be enough. Those that do not consume enough calcium-rich foods may experience bone mineralization problems and fractures. However, studies have found that the risk of fracture is the same for vegans and non-vegetarians alike. Adequate calcium intake appears to be the most important factor in bone health, regardless of dietary preferences. Tofu, turnip and mustard greens, bok choy, and kale are all good sources of calcium. Although calcium is plentiful in spinach and other plants, it is linked to oxalate and hence poorly absorbed.

Fatty Acids

The omega-3 fatty acids are the ones vegetarians are the ones that are most likely to be lacking in (n-3 fats). Vegans consume very little alpha-linolenic acid, the plant form of omega-3 fats. An adequate consumption of n-3 fats has been linked to a lower risk of coronary artery disease and stroke. Foods high in n-3 fatty acids must be prioritised. Among them are ground flax seeds, flax oil, walnuts, and canola oil. Essential fatty acids are fatty acids that humans must ingest in order to sustain good health because our bodies cannot produce them. Only two essential fatty acids have been identified: linoleic acid (an omega-6 fatty acid) and alpha-linolenic acid (an omega-3 fatty acid).

Conclusion

Preparation, label reading, and adherence to rules are all required for a well-balanced vegan diet. Patients who desire to eat a plant-based diet should consume a wide range of fruits and vegetables, as well as beans, legumes, seeds, nuts, and whole grains, while avoiding or restricting animal products, added fats, oils, and refined, processed carbs. Patients who move to a plant-based diet might expect to take less drugs for a range of chronic conditions, lose weight, have a lower risk of cancer, and die from ischemic heart disease. A plant-based diet is a way of life that is suited to each individual, rather than an all-or-nothing strategy.

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